

REVOLUTIONIZING HEALTHCARE: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICAL SCIENCES AND ITS FUTURE IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract-Artificial intelligence is changing quickly the medical sciences, which is providing substantial improvements in medication development, patient monitoring, diagnosis, and treatment planning. The present and future aspects regarding artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare is thoroughly reviewed in this paper, which also highlights important technological advancements like machine learning, natural language processing, rule based expert systems, physical robots, robotic process automation. Notwithstanding these developments, there are still many obstacles to overcome before AI can be fully incorporated into medical practice. These obstacles include worries about data privacy, security risks, and moral dilemmas including algorithmic prejudice. Looking ahead, artificial intelligence in the medical sciences holds the potential for more advancements, better patient outcomes, and more effective healthcare delivery. But in order to fully realize this promise, significant there must be legal frame works in place and ethical deployment must be guaranteed. This analysis highlights how AI has the ability to revolutionize medicine while promoting a balanced approach to its future integration.

Key words: AI (Artificial intelligence), Clinical Manifestation, Types of AI, History.

I.INTRODUCTION

The definition of artificial intelligence is referred to the group of technologies that involves machines and computers to mimic human intelligence. These AI tools are designed to analyse various health data type, ranging from patient data utilizing multi-omics approaches to clinical, behavioural, environmental, and drug data, along with information found in biomedical literature. (1) In a recent report by the National academy of medicine (NAM) regarding the present and future landscape of AI in health care highlighted “Unprecedented opportunities” for enhancing specialist care. They emphasized the valuable assistance AI offers in addressing human limitations, such as fatigue and inattention, while mitigating the risks associated with machine errors. The report underscores the importance of exercising difficulty in adoption of AI technologies in medical sciences., while acknowledging the significant importance. The digitization of data of health and the widespread utilization of technology are creating advancements in AI development and adoption within the healthcare systems. However, the challenges are present like integrating multi modal data, ensuring security, addressing issues related to federated learning, optimizing model performance, mitigating bias may hinder the widespread implementation of AI in medical sciences. (2)

The introduction of Artificial intelligence into medicine prompts a clear examination of how these technologies might increase the strength of historical and ongoing medical injustice. The COVID -19 pandemic has emphasized the urgency of this considerations, revealing the inappropriate impact on the low income and racial or ethnic minority patients all over the world. This difference echoes the socioeconomic and racial or ethnic divides witnessed during Spanish flu pandemic 10 decades back. Medicines history is marked by persistent inequalities that are not solved. As AI becomes more integrated into the healthcare services, there’s a advantageous need to ensure that these disparities are not perpetuated in our digital future. The fast deployment of Clinical AI systems in pandemic response demands an equally urgent discourse on how these related tools may reinforce and worsen existing healthcare. (3) And the AI is also combines with main aspects that enable us to see it as cognitive, intuitive, logical educational and uplifting An Artificial intelligence system learns by analysing and explaining vast amount of structured and unstructured data. This system also helps in making sense in the world by recognizing the objects and their relationships and making connections as well as assessing the data that enable it to identify.

II.TYPES OF AI IN MEDICAL SCIENCES

An artificial intelligence is a collection of many technologies that have different levels of relevance to the medical field. But the tasks and the specific processes vary widely. And the types of this AI with the high importance of AI technology are described below.(4)

1.MACHINE LEARNING

Figure.1: Machine learning

The use of machine learning statistical technique for fitting models to data and to learn by training models with data.

The automation or support for the communicable and non-communicable diseases for diagnosis are emerged to be one of the main uses of AI in medical sciences and is also the most common type of AI. (5) So, Machine learning is considered as one of the broad techniques with the many core approaches with different versions of it with AI. The most common application of the machine learning in the field of medicine is the precision medicine, which helps in forecasting which treatment plans would be most effective to succeed for the patient based on various attributes from the patient to set the treatment. The training and supervision learning is required for the artificial intelligence and precision medicine application that needs the training data set for which the end variable is known.

Neural networks are the most complicated form of machine learning available since 1960s , which is widely used in the research and in healthcare from many years .And from the decades it has been mainly used to categorize about the patient acquiring the diseases and to predict their susceptibility .This kind of approach categories the problems based on inputs, outputs and the changeable weights or features. Although it has been compared to how neurones interpret signals, the parallel to the brain function is limited. (6)

And specially in medical domain, the machine learning has emerged as a game changer, offering a plethora of transformative applications like medical imaging interpretation, Predictive Analytics for disease management, Accelerated drug discovery. The most difficult forms of machine learning are neural networks and deep learning network models with the many interesting levels of features or variables that detect outcomes. The common use deep learning in the medical field is recognising of conceivably malignant tumors on radiological pictures.

2.NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

Figure.2: Natural language processing

Ever since the year 1960, AI researchers have sought to understand the human language. This Natural language processing (NLP) field encompasses the application of AI in medical sciences. (7)

Some of the applications of the NLP includes speech recognition, text analysis and translation. Basically, there are 2 techniques in order to process natural language Statistical and Semantic.

Statistical NLP uses machine learning, specifically deep learning neural networks which has led to improved recognition accuracy. Learning involves a huge Corpus of language. In healthcare, it is primarily used to create, understand and categorize clinical documentation and research these systems can analyse unstructured clinical notes, generate reports (example for radiological exams), transcribe patient interactions and to perform conversational AI.

3.RULE BASED EXPERT SYSTEMS

Figure.3: Rule based expert systems

In the year 1980, AI was mostly based on expert systems using the rules commercially from those subsequent decades, from past few decades they have been widely used in healthcare for the purpose of clinical decision assistance and continue to do so today. Many EHR (electronic health records) providers now include rules with their systems. Expert systems sometimes require the human experts and knowledge engineers to construct the rules within a certain topics, they even operate effectively to a point and are simple and easy to understand when there are a big number of rules (above several thousand) and the rules begin to conflict with each other and they tend to break down ,Changing rules for a changing domain of knowledge can be a time consuming and challenging, They are slowly being replaced in healthcare by more approaches based technologies are gradually replacing traditional methods in healthcare.(8)

4.PHYSICAL ROBOTS

Figure.4: Physical robots

Over 200,000 industrial robots are installed annually worldwide, Physical robots are by now primarily being used in settings like factories, warehouses, and hospitals, where they carry out specific tasks such as

lifting, welding, assembling objects and delivering supplies. In recent times, Robots have evolved to be more collaborative with humans and easier to train for tasks through physical demonstration. They are also becoming more intelligent by incorporating additional AI capabilities into their operating systems. It is anticipated that, over time the same advancements in AI seen in other areas will be integrated into physical robots, enhancing their capabilities and intelligence further. This suggests a future where robots will continue to play increasingly sophisticated roles alongside humans in various industries. Surgical robots which received initial approval in the USA in 2000, enhance Surgeons capabilities by providing them in advanced tools and capabilities by providing them with advanced tools and capabilities. These robots allow surgeons to perform procedures with greater precision and minimal invasiveness, enabling tasks like creating precise incisions and suturing wounds with high accuracy.

It's important to note that while surgical robots offer significant assistance, crucial decisions during procedures are still made by human surgeons. Common surgical applications for robotic surgery include gynaecological procedures, head and neck surgery as well as prostate surgery. In these areas, robotic assistance can lead to improved outcomes and reduced patients' recovery periods showcasing the evolving role of technology in modern healthcare practices. (8)

5.ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION

Figure.5: Robotic process automation

Robotic process automation (RPA) is a technology that utilizes software robots or bots to automate repetitive and rule-based tasks traditionally performed by humans in business processes. These bots help in mimicking human actions such as navigating through software applications, entering data, processing transactions and communicating with other systems. With the use of this technology, administratively related structured digital tasks are completed, unlike other forms of AI, RPA is characterised by its cost effectiveness, ease of programming and transparency in operation.

Despite its name, RPA does not use actual robots; instead, it relies on computer programs running on servers. These programs utilize a combination of workflow management, business rules, and integration with user interface of information systems to automate tasks in a manner resembling human interaction. In medical sciences, RPA is utilized for repetitive purposes as updating patient information and prior authorization, billing processes. When combined with technologies like image recognition. RPA can retrieve data from faxed documents or other image-based sources enabling the automated input of information into transactional systems. This integration of RPA with complementary technologies enhances efficiency and accuracy in healthcare operations, reducing manual effort and potential errors in data handling.(8)

III. HISTORY OF AI IN MEDICINE

Figure.6: History of artificial intelligence in medicine

AI in medicine has drastically evolved in the previous 50 years. Since the evolution of Machine learning has expanded with many applications that has helped in advancing the opportunities for personalised medicines than algorithm-only based medicine. For the diagnosis of medicines the prediction models have been employed, Prediction of therapeutic response and potentially preventive medicine in the future. Improved illness and therapeutic outcomes, increased efficiency in clinical operations and provider workflow, and improved diagnostic accuracy and overall patient data outcomes.

Below is a chronological account of evolution of AI platforms in medicine, categorized into distinct time periods marked by significant transformations. (9)

1950s-1970s

The development of robots with the capacity to draw conclusions or make decisions that humans could only make previously. But in the year 1961, **General Motors** Universale, the first industrial robot arm, went on to do the automated diecasting on the assembly line.

Joseph weizenbam presented ELIZA in the year 1964. ELIZA could imitate human speech by pattern correspondence and replacement matching techniques employing Natural language processing, it provided the foundation for later chatterbots. (9)

In 1966 Shakey developed the first electronic person at Stanford research institute, rather than just doing one-step instructions, Shakey was able to carry out more complex instructions and carryout the appropriate measures. This was a significant advancement in AI and robotics.

Despite the innovations that took place in the field of engineering, Medicine was slow to adopt AI. On the other hand, this early stage was crucial for digitizing data, which later became the basis for AIMS (Artificial intelligence in medicine) expansions and use. The evolution of an analysis and retrieval system for medical literature (MEDLARS) and the web- based search engine PubMed through the National library of medicine (NLM) in 1960s. These resources were crucial for the subsequent advancement of biometric. Eleven clinical informatics and medical record systems were also developed during time to help in the establishment of foundation for the future development of AIM. (9)

1970-2000s

The term AI winter characterises a period of decreased funding and interest resulting in fewer significant advancement. Two major winters are recognised; one in the late 1970s due to the perceived AI limitations and another in the late 1980s and to early 1990s due to high costs of developing and maintaining digital databases. Despite having general interest, Collaboration among AI pioneers persisted. Soul Amarel established the Research resource on computers in biomedicine at Rutgers university 1971. The creation of the medical experiment at Stanford university AI in medicine (SUMEX_AIM) system in 1973 facilitated networking among researchers. These collaborations led to the inaugural NIH-sponsored AI in medicine workshop 1975 at Rutgers university, marking the beginning of collective efforts in AIM.

The CASNET model was among the pioneering prototypes showcasing the application of AI in medicine, developed at Rutgers university, it was a consultation program designed for glaucoma.

The CASNET system comprised 3 unique program model development consulting and a database collaboratively built and managed. This model enabled the application of disease details about specific

patients, offering physicians guidance on patient management. Officially unveiled at 1976 meeting of the academy of ophthalmology Las Vegas Nevada, it marked a significant milestone in the integration of AI into medical practice.

Early in the 1970s, MYCIN an AI system utilizing backward chaining was developed with about 600 rules in its knowledge base, MYCIN could suggest bacterial pathogens and antibiotic treatments considering the patient data. This system inspired EMYCIN which established the framework for INTERNIST-1, assisting primary care physicians for diagnostic purposes.

A decision assistance system called DXplain was produced by the university of Massachusetts in 1986.

The application depending on the symptoms supplied, generates a differential diagnosis; it also serves as an electronic medical textbook containing the comprehensive illness descriptions and supplementary sources. It provided information on approximately 500 diseases /it has now covered more than 2400 ailments till now. Along with the above-mentioned technological advancements, a rise in interest in artificial intelligence during the late 1990s, especially in the medical field helped in the current development of the Artificial intelligence in machine learning. (9)

2000- 2020s

In 2007, IBM unveiled Watson, an open-domain question answering system that clinched victory on the game show Jeopardy! In 2011, competing against human contestants. Unlike traditional systems reliant on forward or backward reasoning, Watson, powered by Deep QA technology, harnessed natural language processing (NLP) and diverse searches to sift through unstructured data, providing likely answers. This technology, being more accessible, easier to maintain and cost-effective, opened avenues for evidence-based clinical decision-making by drawing insights from electronic medical records and other sources.

In 2017, Bakkar successfully employed IBM Watson to determine the new RNA-binding proteins linked to amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), showcasing its versatility in medical research. This, coupled with advancements in computer hardware and software, propelled the rapid growth of AI in medicine. Natural Language processing (NLP) also revolutionized chatbots, transforming them from superficial interactions to meaningful interfaces. Examples include Apple's Siri (2011) and Amazon's Alexa (2014). Specific applications emerged, such as Pharma Bot (2015) for paediatric medication education and Mandy (2017) for automated patient intake in primary care patients.

Deep learning (DL) emerged as a pivotal advancement in AI in medicine, surpassing traditional machine learning (ML) by enabling autonomous data classification. Overcoming past limitations like overfitting, DL gained traction in the 2000s due to larger datasets and enhanced computing power. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a type of DL algorithm, revolutionized image processing by mimicking the neural connectivity within the human brain. Renowned CNN algorithms like Le- NET, Alex Net and Resnet are now widely applied in medical imaging and diagnostics, Propelling Ais impact in healthcare.(9)

IV. CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS

Artificial intelligence is being most widely used in a wide range of clinical settings in the medical sciences to improve patient care and diagnosis, treatment and delivery of healthcare. Key clinical manifestations of AI in medical sciences include the following

Figure.7: Main areas of AI application in Medicine (10)

Artificial intelligence in Gynaecologic cancers

Hardly little progress in artificial intelligence has been made in the field of gynaecologic oncology. In contrast to other medical specialities utilizing AI technologies, including endoscopy, gynaecologic oncology falls short in this regard. This includes,

1. Early detection and identification:

Artificial intelligence algorithms analyse medical imaging data, such as ultrasound, MRI, CT scans, to detect and characterize gynaecologic tumours at an early stage. This aids in timely diagnosis and treatment initiation.

2. Image Analysis and segmentation:

Machine learning techniques are used to precisely segment and analyse tumour regions within imaging data. This assists clinicians in assessing tumour size, location, and response to treatment.

3. Pathology and Histology:

AI based algorithms can automate the analysis of histopathological images, helping pathologists identify and classify cancerous cells with high accuracy. This streamlines the diagnostic process and enhances consistency.

4. Personalized treatment planning:

AI models integrate patient-specific data, including genomic profiles and treatment strategies. This may involve predicting response to chemotherapy or identifying targeted therapy options.

5. Prognostic Modelling:

Machine learning models can predict patient outcome based on a combination of clinical factors, biomarkers, and imaging data. This assists clinicians in making informed decisions regarding treatment and follow up care.

6. Radiomics and predictive Analytics:

Radiomic analysis, which involves extracting quantitative attributes extracted from medical pictures, is utilized to develop predictive models for gynaecologic cancers. These models can forecast treatment response and recurrence risk.

7. Supporting Clinical Decision-Making:

AI-powered decision support systems provide clinicians with evidence-based recommendations for treatment planning and follow-up care. This can lead to more effective and personalised management of gynaecologic cancers.

8.Remote Monitoring and Telemedicine:

AI technologies enable remote monitoring of patients undergoing cancer treatment, allowing for timely intervention in case of complications or adverse events. Telemedicine platforms powered by AI facilitate virtual consultations and follow-ups.

The integration of AI in gynaecologic oncology holds great promise for advancing precision medicine, improving patient outcomes, optimizing healthcare professionals are essential to harness the full potential of these technologies in clinical practice.

Artificial intelligence in pulmonology

AI has been used to a tool that assesses chest CT images for lung cancer; in this tool, the AI system finds patterns in changes that are both temporally and spatially distributed, as well as changes in nodule and nonnodular characteristics, to precisely direct therapeutic care in a long-term screening program and forecast 3-year lung cancer risk.

In addition to using image analysis, the diagnosis of respiratory diseases including asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) requires gathering a patient's medical history, and physical examination in addition to potential imaging (X-rays, CT scans, bronchoscopies) and pulmonary function testing (to a certain extent). AI might be able to help doctors in particular, even though respiratory doctors are capable of interpreting variances in pulmonary function tests and analysing images. (11)

Artificial Intelligence in Cardiology

With significant advancements in signal processing, picture segmentation, and structured data analysis, recently in almost all domains of cardiology, including some noticeable develop in terms of AI in medicine, cardiology is at the forefront. 34 Significant progresses have been achieved recently in risk assessment, automated imaging study interpretation, and ECG analysis. As successful as this collaboration turns out to be, artificial intelligence in cardiology and medicine as a whole has a bright future. (12)

Artificial Intelligence in orthopaedic

AI is transforming orthopaedics by enhancing diagnostics, improving surgical precision, and optimizing the treatment of patient and the key applications include in Diagnostic Imaging AI improves the interpretation, MRIs, and CT scans, detecting subtle abnormalities for earlier, accurate diagnoses. In Surgical planning and navigation, AI helps with creation of comprehensive surgical plans and offers on the spot direction while performing operations. And in predictive analytics AI makes individualized treatment plans possible by forecasting patient outcomes and possible consequences. Robotic surgery, AI improves

the precision and control of robotic devices used in spine operations and joint replacements. In rehabilitation and monitoring wearables and AI powered applications keep track of patient's recuperation to guarantee successful rehabilitation. And when it comes to research and development analyses massive datasets, and speeds up research, resulting in better orthopaedic devices and innovative therapies. (13)

Artificial intelligence in Hepatology

Even while AI-based models have a lot of potential to help patients with liver illness, there are a few issues that must be resolved before moving further, these models from the lab to the patient's bed. A growing number of people are worried that using computer algorithms in healthcare could create or exacerbate prejudices against disadvantaged groups and lead to health inequalities. AI algorithms have the potential to introduce a number of biases, such as those pertaining to the choice of the clinical research challenge, biases in data collecting and variable selection, and biases in the creation and application of algorithms after they have been developed. Prospective AI-based randomized clinical trials are required to conclusively show the added benefit of AI models in enhancing patient outcomes before they can be extensively implemented in hepatology. Numerous studies in the field of endoscopy have shown how computer-aided algorithms can improve the rate at which polyps and adenomas are detected during colonoscopy.(14)

Artificial intelligence in Neurology

AI is revolutionising neurology by enhancing diagnostic accuracy through improved interpretation of MRI, CT and PET scan, enabling early detection of conditions like tumours and multiple sclerosis. Predictive analytics aid in managing diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson by forecasting disease progression. AI-powered robotic systems increase precision in neurosurgery, while wearable devices monitor chronic conditions like epilepsy in real-time. Additionally, AI accelerates drug development by analysing large datasets to identify new treatments. Despite challenges in data privacy and system integration, AIs advancements are significantly improving patient care and outcomes in neurology. (15)

V. FUTURE MANAGEMENT

Integrative Analysis

The future generation of scientists, as envisioned by Francis Collins in his vision about the precision medicine program, will "provide innovative methods for identifying, quantifying, and evaluating a broad spectrum of biomedical data, such as molecular, genomic, cellular, clinical, behavioural, physiological, and environmental factors, according to Wang et al. A health condition can be described from several

angles by data from various modalities, and by integratively mining such heterogeneous data, comprehensive and holistic insights into health can be gained. AI in medical field has been the subject of more studies and initiatives in recent years. These include combining various clinical data aspects, connecting biorepositories with clinical data, and creating links between clinical data and pharmaceutical research and development. More importantly, creating successful AI algorithms for health requires combining data and understanding. Unlike other computer-related topics like vision and Patient data is frequently sparse and subject to broad variation, unlike voice analysis, where enormous data sets can be acquired. Furthermore, health issues in the actual world are frequently complicated. In order to mitigate this issue, the knowledge of biologists and clinicians is required to guide the model's learning process and prevent the model from overfitting the data. (16)

Model transparency

Rule-based systems and other conventional AI technologies are quite interpretable. Although deep learning models and other recent AI technologies can achieve outstanding quantitative performance, they are still primarily regarded as black cartons. The necessity of model interpretability has been the subject of numerous discussions lately. For instance, DL pioneer Geoff Hinton stated in a recent interview that lawmakers shouldn't insist on making sure people understand every detail of a particular AI algorithm's operation as "humans can't describe how they operate, for most of the things they do." Poursabzi-Sangdeh et al investigated the significance of model interpretability to users through a controlled randomized experiment. Remarkably, the findings demonstrated that there was no discernible variation in users' confidence in black-box and models that are transparent. Furthermore, "people's capacity to identify significant errors in models was hampered by increased transparency." In support of black-box models, Holm (17) drew a comparison to the highly subjective human decision-making process, where choices are made "out of their own 'deep learning.'" Because of this, "neuroscience faces the same interpretability challenge as computer science today."

Model security

Typically, we discuss the significance of safeguarding the privacy and safety of health data, particularly the information on specific patients. As the quantity of AI models in the healthcare industry rises, additionally we must be mindful of the models' possible security risks. Adversarial assault, which is the procedure for creating data that can perplex algorithms for machine learning and lead to less-than-ideal or even wrong judgments, is one example. Sitawarin et al, for instance, showed how pollution on traffic signs may readily trick autonomous driving systems. Sun et al.'s research shown how even little changes to a patient's electronic health record's lab

values can drastically change the predictor's ability to estimate death, even if the predictor is otherwise highly trained. Yeahll sendll (18) Finlayson and colleagues offer a more comprehensive analysis of the possible worries regarding the "incentives for more complex hostile attacks" in the medical field. In light of medical adversarial attacks, the authors of this article believe that it is critical that (i) medical professionals be aware of this potential risk; (ii) AI researchers develop effective defense mechanisms; and (iii) policy makers consider the potential model security risk when creating new regulatory frameworks.

Federated Learning

Federated learning is able to help with this difficulty. Konečný et al. state that Federated Learning is an ML scenario. where the objective is to use training data spread across numerous customers to train a high-quality centralized model. These customers frequently have slow and erratic network connections. The creation of federated health AI technologies is crucial and extremely challenging. A privacy-preserving federated patient similarity learning approach was developed by Lee et al. and tested on MIMIC III data. They verified that appropriate homomorphic encryption of patient data may, in fact, maintain the Caliber of patient similarity metrics in a federated environment.(19)

Data bias

All AI models require samples of training data. Generally, the training sample size that is collected from patients is insufficiently large to fully represent the variety of people and the intricacies of their medical issues. Patients at different hospitals often cannot be treated using the same model that was trained on patients from one facility. This problem is commonly known as the bias present in the data, and it continues to be one of the key obstacles facing AI in the healthcare industry. Khullar, noted that this kind of bias can exacerbate health inequities. The collection of sizable and varied patient data sets is one strategy to lessen bias.

A few instances of these initiatives are the Patient-Centered Outcomes Research Institute (PCORI) established the national clinical research network PCORnet, which at the moment consists of 13 clinical data research networks (CDRNs) that gather longitudinal patient data from various health systems around the country. These initiatives provide the large-scale, diversified data sets that are necessary to build reliable, broadly applicable AI models. Researchers can additionally lessen bias in the process of building the model by employing techniques like the counterfactual Gaussian Process, which is designed to carry out "what-if" analysis for personalized treatment planning in addition to risk prediction. (20)

VI.CONCLUSION

AI showing an advance level in medical sciences as well as its replacement of humans in treatment of diseases especially in oncology, pulmonology, Cardiovascular, orthopaedics, hepatology, and neurology with the AI technologies like Machine learning, natural language processing, physical robots, rule based expert systems, physical robots, and robotic automation process. AI in medical sciences promises to

revolutionize healthcare by improving diagnostic precision, optimizing treatment plans, and enhancing patient monitoring and drug development processes. Despite these advancements, careful implementation is necessary to address critical concerns about the privacy of data, security, and ethical considerations. The future of AI in medical sciences looks bright, with expected innovations that could further transform healthcare delivery and patient outcomes. But achieving this potential would need creating strong regulatory structures, encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration, and ensuring that AI systems are designed and used ethically and fairly. By tackling these challenges and fostering an environment of ongoing innovation and responsible usage, AI can significantly improve the effectiveness and effectiveness of medical care, leading to better health outcomes for patients globally. This conclusion underscores the potential for AI to transform medical sciences while highlighting the need for responsible and ethical implementation to achieve its full benefits.

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